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Optimization of Moving Bed Membrane Bioreactor Process for Improved Water and Nutrient Recovery from Domestic Wastewater

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Abstract:	<p>Three different MBMBR configurations were compared under various loadings. The studied configurations were configuration-1: one MBBR+MBR, configuration-2: two serially connected MBBRs+MBR, and configuration-3: two serially connected MBBRs+MBR with sludge recycling to the second MBBR. The first MBBR showed high COD removal rates (up to 21 g-COD/m².d). In configurations-2 and -3, ammonium oxidation rates in MBBR-2 were 0.67 and 0.91 g- NH₄⁺-N/(m².d), respectively. Hybridizing suspended and attached growth processes improved the nitrification rate. In the MBR, complete nitrification was attained throughout the study, together with increasing total nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations due to biomass decay at long SRT. The serial arrangement of MBBRs may allow for a more economical design, as the attached biomass in the MBBR-1 increased appreciably (> 20 g-SS/m²) with the increasing COD loading. Configuration-3 gave the best performance among the studied alternatives in terms of water reuse and nutrient recycling.</p>
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Dear Editor,

Please find the manuscript titled “*Optimization of Moving Bed Membrane Bioreactor Process for Improved Water and Nutrient Recovery from Domestic Wastewater*” to be considered for publication in *Journal of Water Process Engineering*.

The manuscript has not been published before and is not under consideration in any journal. The paper was not previously submitted *Journal of Water Process Engineering*. We also note that all the authors mutually agree to submit it to *Journal of Water Process Engineering*. The total length of the manuscript is 8068 words.

Novelty of the Study

The main novelty of the study is optimizing the moving bed biofilm membrane bioreactor (MBMBR) process for water and nutrient recovery for agricultural irrigation. Properly treated wastewater containing nutrients can be considered a valuable source for plant cultivation. Hence, rather than removing the nutrients using various biological and chemical processes, recycling them for agricultural purposes will decrease treatment costs, pollution in receiving bodies, and fertilizer consumption in agricultural activities. This study is a part of the PRIMA project, which aims at securing sustainable food by maximizing water and nutrient recovery from domestic wastewater for agricultural reuse or recovery. In the study, nitrogen and phosphorus recovery was maximized by employing three different MBMBR configurations to evaluate the impact of staging and hybridizing biofilm and suspended biomass in a single reactor. Complete nitrification and ~80% P recovery were attained throughout the study, together with increasing total nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations due to biomass decay at long SRT.

Sincerely Yours,
On behalf of all authors,
Erkan Sahinkaya, PhD

Highlights

1. Three MBMBR configurations were tested for COD removal and nitrification.
2. Serially connected MBBRs performed better than single MBBR.
3. COD and NH_4^+ -N oxidation rates in MBBRs were 21 and 0.91 g/(m².d), respectively.
4. Hybridizing suspended and attached processes performed better for nitrification.
5. MBMBR is a promising process for water reuse, N and P recycling for irrigation.

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3 **Optimization of Moving Bed Membrane Bioreactor Process for Improved Water and**
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5 **Nutrient Recovery from Domestic Wastewater**
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Abstract

Three different MBMBR configurations were compared under various loadings. The studied configurations were configuration-1: one MBBR+MBR, configuration-2: two serially connected MBBRs+MBR, and configuration-3: two serially connected MBBRs+MBR with sludge recycling to the second MBBR. The first MBBR showed high COD removal rates (up to 21 g-COD/m².d). In configurations-2 and -3, ammonium oxidation rates in MBBR-2 were 0.67 and 0.91 g- NH₄⁺-N/(m².d), respectively. Hybridizing suspended and attached growth processes improved the nitrification rate. In the MBR, complete nitrification was attained throughout the study, together with increasing total nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations due to biomass decay at long SRT. The serial arrangement of MBBRs may allow for a more economical design, as the attached biomass in the MBBR-1 increased appreciably (> 20 g-SS/m²) with the increasing COD loading. Configuration-3 gave the best performance among the studied alternatives in terms of water reuse and nutrient recycling.

Keywords: moving bed membrane bioreactor; moving bed biofilm reactor; nitrification; water reuse; nutrient recovery

1. INTRODUCTION

Considering that around 70% of the water used worldwide is for irrigation, it can be understood how important it is to reuse properly treated domestic wastewater for irrigation, which decreases consumption of water resources and discharged amounts of wastewater [1]. Water scarcity, being a global problem, is estimated to affect 40% of the world population by 2050 [2] and hence, wastewater reuse, after proper treatment, may alleviate this problem. However, the standards for both reuse and discharge are getting more stringent, and the conventional

1 treatment processes may not always be appropriate due to the lack of reliability of treated water
2 quality [3].
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5 In order to meet the increasing reuse and discharge standards on organics, nutrients, recalcitrant
6 compounds, and pathogens, new biological processes based on the suspended biomass and
7 biofilm [4] or their combinations should be developed. Therefore, there is a need to develop
8 innovative technologies for both newly established treatment plants, and upgrading existing
9 CAS, considering that water pollution is a global problem and freshwater resources contain a
10 wide variety of chemicals of concern [5]. The biofilm processes may be considered an
11 alternative approach for CAS, mainly due to the high biomass diversity and concentration,
12 decreased volume requirement, less sludge generation, high performance, and high tolerance to
13 toxicity [6,7]. A wide range of biofilm-based processes, including rotating biological contactors
14 [8], trickling filters, submerged fixed film processes, and fluidized bed bioreactors [9], have
15 been used in wastewater treatment [10]. However, several operational problems, including high
16 mass transfer resistance, difficulty in generating biofilm evenly on attached media, not using
17 the whole reactor volume, clogging due to overgrowth of biofilm, and mechanical failure, have
18 been reported depending on the biofilm process and the operational conditions [10].
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40 The moving bed bioreactor process (MBBR) was developed as an alternative biofilm process,
41 where biofilm develops on plastic carriers, at the beginning of the 1990s [11,12]. The MBBR
42 process offers several benefits over the CAS and aforementioned biofilm processes, as biofilm
43 carriers freely move within the bioreactor, eliminating clogging. Additionally, the MBBR
44 process increases oxygen and nutrient mass transfers, nitrification performance, and lowers area
45 requirements [12–14]. In the MBBR process, specialized biofilm on the carriers develops,
46 allowing for higher volumetric removal rates compared to the CAS processes [12]. Easy
47 upgrading of low-performing CAS processes with minimal civil and mechanical work to the
48 MBBR processes for improving their performance and capacity, especially for nitrification, is
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1 a distinct advantage of the process [13,15]. Whereas the main operational challenge of the
2 MBBR process is sludge separation, [14], which may even worsen at high loadings [16].
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5 Another alternative process to CAS is the membrane bioreactor (MBR) process, which has been
6 widely used due to its several benefits, including better effluent quality, lower space
7 requirements, and making water reuse easier [17,18]. The MBR process combines the
8 biological process with the physical separation of micro- or ultra-porous membranes, resulting
9 in high effluent quality, as the process can even remove viruses by 4 logs depending on
10 membrane pore size [19]. Therefore, the MBR permeate may directly be used for irrigation.
11 However, membrane fouling remains the major drawback of the process [20,21], which may
12 decrease its widespread use.
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24 Integrating MBR and MBBR processes, the moving bed membrane bioreactor (MBMBR)
25 [17,22], may solve the operational problems of each process, i.e., the settling of MBBR sludge
26 and fouling in the MBR process. Leiknes & Ødegaard [23] reported that the MBMBR process
27 performed much better, especially in terms of filtration flux, compared to conventional MBR.
28 This improvement in MBMBR processes originates from decreased cake resistance compared
29 to conventional MBR processes due to reduced suspended biomass concentration [22]. Hence,
30 the MBMBR process can combine the unique advantages of the MBR and MBBR processes
31 while eliminating the disadvantages of each process. The MBMBR process can exhibit high
32 removal efficiencies with a considerable decrease in MBR fouling. [24] reported that MBMBR
33 performed better compared to MBR for micropollutant removals, together with a lower fouling
34 tendency, which can be attributed to lower soluble microbial products (SMP) concentrations.
35 Decrease in fouling in the MBMBRs, compared to conventional MBRs, was also reported by
36 [25]. However, contradictory results have been reported in the literature as the biochemical
37 characteristics of biomass and the supernatant impact the filtration performance [26–28]. For
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1 example, Yang et al. [27] observed that cake resistance in the MBMBR was higher compared
2 to that in the MBR due to filamentous growth in the MBMBR.
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5 Properly treated wastewater containing nutrients can also be considered a valuable source for
6 plant cultivation [29]. Hence, rather than removing the nutrients using various biological and
7 chemical processes, recycling them for agricultural purposes will decrease treatment costs,
8 pollution in receiving bodies, and fertilizer consumption in agricultural activities. Hence,
9 treatment processes allowing for both water reuse and nutrient recycling should be developed
10 for sustainability.
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20 Combining suspended and attached processes in one reactor, which is called the integrated fixed
21 film activated sludge (IFAS) process [14,30] increases process performance (see Saidulu et al.
22 [31] for more information). In the existing literature, the MBR and MBBR processes were
23 combined in various configurations. Despite the substantial advantages of the MBMBR
24 processes in wastewater treatment, their full-scale applications are still limited. In particular,
25 there is a gap in the literature about the optimization of MBMBR process configuration in terms
26 of nitrification capacity to recover water and nutrients for irrigation. Hence, this study aims to
27 investigate the performances of different MBMBR process configurations, including one or
28 serially connected MBBRs, in the presence or absence of sludge recycling. In the current study,
29 nitrification was intended without nitrate removal to evaluate the performance of the process
30 for nutrient recycling for agricultural irrigation purposes.
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47 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

48 **2.1. Experimental Setup**

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51 A moving bed membrane bioreactor (MBMBR) (Fig. 1) operated in three different
52 configurations was used in the study. In the first 10 days, only MBBR at an HRT of 24 h was
53 operated in the absence of its connection to MBR to allow the development of biofilm on the
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1 plastic media. Then, the MBR was put into operation, and experiments were started for three
2 different MBMBR configurations.
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5 In the first configuration (configuration-1), two bioreactors with an equal volume of 7.0 L were
6 used, one for MBBR and the other for MBR. 50% of the whole MBBR volume was filled with
7 biocarriers having 25 mm diameter and 12 mm depth. The surface area of the biocarriers, which
8 are made of high-density polyethylene, was $600 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$. A total of 400 biocarriers were used in
9 the MBBR. In the MBR, a submerged hollow fiber ultrafiltration (0.04 μm pore size) ZeeWeed
10 500M–1M membrane module with a total surface area of 0.23 m^2 was used [32].
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20 In the second configuration (configuration-2), two serially connected MBBRs, each having 3.5
21 L, were used. The biocarriers used in the first configuration were halved and utilized in the
22 MBBRs. Hence, a total of 200 biocarriers were used per MBBR, corresponding to a 50% filling
23 ratio. In order to initiate biofilm formation in the second MBBR (MBBR-2), sludge was
24 recycled from the MBR reactor only for two weeks. Then, sludge recycling from the MBR was
25 discontinued.
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35 In the third configuration (configuration-3), biomass was recycled from the MBR to the second
36 MBBR with a flow rate equal to that of the feeding (2.4 L/h). All the bioreactors were aerated
37 to have complete mixing and dissolved oxygen (DO) concentrations $\geq 4 \text{ mg/L}$. Three peristaltic
38 pumps were used to feed, draw permeate, and recycle suspended sludge (in the third
39 configuration only). Transmembrane pressure (TMP) in the MBR was measured continuously.
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48 **2.2. Operational Conditions**

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51 A synthetic wastewater prepared according to [33] was used throughout the study. COD, TN,
52 $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$, and total phosphorus concentrations in the feed averaged 523 ± 27 , 61 ± 1 , 32 ± 2 , and
53 $5.5 \pm 0.5 \text{ mg/L}$, respectively. The operational conditions of the MBMBR under different
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1 configurations are provided in Table 1. Throughout the bioreactor operation, SRT in the MBR
2 was maintained at 20 days by wasting the excess sludge from the MBR tank daily.
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5 In the first configuration, the impact of HRT on the process performance was evaluated. The
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7 HRTs in the MBBR and MBR were kept the same at 12 and 6 h in periods-1 and -2, respectively.
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10 The filtration flux was increased from 2.5 LMH in period-1 to 5 LMH in period-2 by doubling
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12 the feed flow rate. In the second configuration, where an additional MBBR (MBBR-2) was
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14 added to the system, and HRTs in the MBBRs were kept the same at 3 h first (period-3) and
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16 then decreased to 1.5 h (period-4). The corresponding HRTs and fluxes in the MBR were 6, 3
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18 h, and 5, 10 LMH, respectively. In the last configuration (configuration-3), the impact of the
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20 sludge recycling from the MBR to the MBBR-2, especially on the nitrification performance,
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22 was evaluated. In this configuration, both attached and suspended biomass were maintained in
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24 the MBBR-2.
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29 The MBMBR process was operated for 270 days under various conditions (Table 1).
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31 Operational conditions were changed after reaching the steady-state condition, which took at
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33 least two SRTs of operation.
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46 **2.3. Estimation of sludge production and SRT**

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49 The observed yield (Y_{obs}) in the MBBR-1 was calculated using the following equation [32],
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51 assuming that the biofilm on the media was under steady-state conditions, i.e., the attached
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53 biomass concentration during the operating period stayed unchanged.
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$$57 Y = \frac{Px}{Q.(S_0-S)} = \frac{MLVSS}{(S_0-S)} \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

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Where P_x and Q represent daily sludge generation (g/d) and flow rate (L/d), S_o and S are the inlet and outlet of soluble COD concentrations (g/L), respectively. As the sludge was not settled and recycled to the MBBR-1, Y_{obs} can simply be calculated using Equation 1.

SRT was calculated using the following equation, both for MBBRs and the whole MBMBR process.

$$SRT = \frac{(\text{Suspended biomass amount (g)} + \text{attached biomass amount (g)})}{\text{Daily sludge generation (g/d)}} \quad \text{Equation (2)}$$

2.4. Analytical Methods

During the operation of the bioreactor, samples were collected from each reactor and permeate regularly for the measurement of pH, alkalinity, COD, NO_3^- -N, NO_2^- -N, TN, NH_4^+ -N, TP, PO_4^{3-} -P, mixed liquor suspended solids (MLSS), and mixed liquor volatile suspended solids (MLVSS). Supernatants from the different compartments were sampled for soluble microbial products (SMP) and extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) analyses. The tightly and loosely bound EPS, carbohydrate, and protein contents of the SMP and EPS were also measured. Sludge samples from the membrane unit (MBR process) were also sampled for additional filtration tests, including supernatant filterability, capillary suction time (CST), and resistance to filtration, in order to investigate the relationship between sludge/supernatant characteristics and filtration performance. Viscosity was also measured on the sludge samples obtained from the membrane unit. The critical flux, above which membrane fouling occurs, was also determined according to [32]. TMP in the MBR was monitored throughout the operation. Physical and/or chemical membrane cleanings, according to [34], were applied when TMP exceeded around 400 mbar. Additionally, the attached biomass concentration on the biocarriers was measured regularly.

In the liquid samples, alkalinity, COD, MLSS, and MLVSS concentrations were measured according to [35]. The concentrations of NO_3^- -N, NO_2^- -N and PO_4^{3-} -P were measured using ion

1 chromatography Dionex ICS-5000+ (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). TN, NH₄⁺-N and TP
2 concentrations were determined using HACH kits. In the capillary suction time (CST) and
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4 viscosity measurements, Type 304M Capillary Suction Timer (Triton Electronics Ltd.,
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6 England) and DV-E viscometer (Brookfield Ltd., Canada) were used, respectively. Specific
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8 resistance to filtration (SRF), and sludge filterability (SF) tests were performed as described by
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10 [36]. SMP and EPS measurements were conducted according to Yilmaz et al. [32]. The amount
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12 of suspended solids on attached biomass was regularly determined by drying 3-5 randomly
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14 collected biocarriers from MBBRs at 60 °C for two days.
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20 **3. Results and Discussion**

21 **3.1. Organic Matter Removal Performance of Different MBMBR Configurations**

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25 In configuration-1, where MBBR and MBR were used in series, each bioreactor was operated
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27 under two different HRTs of 12 h (period-1) and 6 h (period-2) (Fig. 1 and Table 1). In the first
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29 period, the feed and the MBBR effluent COD concentrations averaged 528±28 and 37±17
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31 mg/L, respectively, corresponding to 93% removal efficiency (Fig. 2). In the MBR process,
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33 average COD concentrations within the supernatant and permeate were 25±11 and 12±8 mg/L,
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35 respectively. Total COD removal efficiency in the bioreactor reached around 98%. The soluble
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37 COD decrease during the filtration was possibly due to further physical and biological removal
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39 thanks to a cake or gel layer developed on the membrane, as previously noted in many other
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41 studies [32,37]. In period-2, the HRT in each bioreactor of configuration-1 decreased to 6 h. An
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43 operational problem between days 86 and 98 resulted in a significant increase in COD
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45 concentrations of MBBR effluent. Whereas under steady-state conditions, average COD in the
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47 effluent of the MBBR remained 43±15 mg/L, very close to the previous period (37±17 mg/L).
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49 However, the increase in the MBR supernatant was much more noteworthy, as it increased from
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51 25±11 to 101±30 mg/L when the HRT was reduced from 12 to 6 h, respectively (Fig. 2). The
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53 COD concentration in the MBR permeate (22±12 mg/L) was slightly higher than the previous
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period (12 ± 8 mg/L). However, the total COD removal efficiency was still 96%. Hence, halving the HRT in each reactor in the second period did not adversely affect the process efficiency.

In the configuration-2, a second MBBR (MBBR-2) was used to investigate the impact of the serial connection arrangement on the process performance. The volume of each MBBR in the second configuration was half of that in the first configuration. Hence, the total MBBR volume in the second configuration was equal to that of the first configuration. Firstly, HRT in each MBBR was kept equal at 3 h, whereas it was 6 h in the MBR. COD concentrations in the MBBR-1 and MBBR-2 averaged 39 ± 7 and 41 ± 12 mg/L, respectively. Hence, using two MBBRs in series, but at the same total volume, did not change the COD concentration in the effluent of the attached growth bioprocess. In the MBR process, the COD concentration in the supernatant did not change significantly, as it was 97 ± 29 mg/L. The MBR permeate COD decreased appreciably to 9 ± 2 mg/L, corresponding to over 98% removal efficiency. Later in period-4, HRTs in each MBBR and MBR were decreased to 1.5 and 3 h, respectively. Hence, the total HRT of the whole process was 6 h. Decreasing the HRT in the MBBR-1 from 3 to 1.5 h increased the effluent COD concentration from around 40 to 125 ± 14 mg/L. However, the COD concentration in the MBBR-2 decreased to around 45 mg/L. Hence, the second MBBR-2 behaved as a polishing unit. In the supernatant and permeate of the MBR, COD concentrations were 48 ± 15 and 11 ± 4 mg/L, respectively. Hence, halving the HRT in the process did not adversely affect the process performance in terms of COD removal, as it was around 98%.

In period-5, configuration-3 was operated under conditions similar to those in period-4, where configuration-2 was used. In configuration-3, sludge was recycled from the MBR to the MBBR-2 to utilize both suspended and attached growth biomass in the same reactor. The operational condition of the MBBR-1 did not change, and, hence, the effluent COD concentration (137 ± 39 mg/L) was similar to that in the previous period (125 ± 14 mg/L). In the MBBR-2, supernatant, and permeate of MBR, COD concentrations averaged 46 ± 21 , 95 ± 16 , and 11 ± 3 mg/L,

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respectively, under steady-state conditions. Hence, the total COD removal performance was quite similar to that in the previous period (period-4) of configuration-2.

In the MBBR-1 process, the COD loading rate increased with decreasing HRT and reached 27-28 g-COD/(m².d) in periods-4 and -5 (Fig. S.1). The COD removal rates in these periods averaged 21 g-COD/(m².d), corresponding to around 75% removal. In agreement with this finding, Ødegaard [12] reported that the soluble COD loading rate should not be higher than 20-25 g-COD/(m².d).

3.2. Variations in pH and Alkalinity

In the feed, the pH and alkalinity averaged 7.6±0.2 and 512±27 mg-CaCO₃/L, respectively. Nitrification generates acidity, which decreases pH and alkalinity. In the MBBR-1, nitrification was not observed throughout the operation, and pH and alkalinity stayed almost constant during the study, averaging 8.4±0.2 and 622±37 mg-CaCO₃/L (Fig. 3).

MBBR-2 was put into operation in period-3 and later. In the first two weeks of period-3, sludge was recycled from MBR to MBBR-2 to seed and allow the biomass to grow on the biocarriers. During this short duration, alkalinity in the MBBR-2 decreased sharply. Alkalinity increased after stopping the sludge recycling. As will be discussed later in Section 3.3., nitrifying biomass developed gradually on the biocarriers in MBBR-2 during period-3, and nitrate concentration reached around 25 mg/L NO₃⁻-N under steady-state operation. As nitrifying biomass developed on the biocarriers, alkalinity gradually decreased, averaging 384±12 mg/L under steady-state conditions (Fig. 3). Hence, around 229 mg/L CaCO₃ alkalinity was consumed during nitrification. Assuming 7.14 mg CaCO₃ is required per mg NH₄⁺-N oxidation, the theoretical alkalinity consumption is 179 mg/L CaCO₃, which is slightly lower than the measured one (229 mg/L CaCO₃). In period-4, nitrification ceased completely with decreasing HRT, which led to increasing alkalinity in the outlet of MBBR-2 back to 590 mg/L CaCO₃. In the last period with

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sludge recycling and partial nitrification in the MBBR-2, pH and alkalinity decreased to 7.9 and 373 mg/L CaCO₃, respectively.

In the MBR permeate, pH and alkalinity averaged 7.9±0.2 and 330±43 mg/L CaCO₃, respectively. In the MBR permeate, the nitrate concentration averaged around 45 mg/L throughout the reactor operation. Considering the whole bioreactor, the theoretical alkalinity consumption was around 321 mg/L CaCO₃. The measured alkalinity consumption, considering the outlet of MBBR-1 (nitrification was not observed) and MBR permeate, was 292 mg/L CaCO₃, which is very close to the theoretically calculated value with around a 10% difference.

3.3. Nitrification Performance of Different MBMBR Configurations

In the first period, in which HRTs of MBBR and MBR were 12 h, the total nitrogen (TN) concentration and the corresponding ammonia concentration in the influent were 61±1 mg-N/L and 32 mg-N/L, respectively. The average surface total nitrogen and COD loading rates (Fig. S.1) were 0.4 g-N/(m².d) and 3.52 g-COD/(m².d) for MBBR-1. MBBR-1 only performed COD removal in all configurations, and no nitrification was observed throughout the study because of the low SRT and high surface organic loading rates (3.5-28 g-COD/(m².d)) (Table 1 and Fig. S.1). It is reported that the nitrification almost stops at organic loading rates exceeding 5 g-BOD/(m².d) [38], and C/N ratio should be ≤ 1 [39]. Except for period 1, in which the surface COD loading rate was 3.5 g/(m².d), COD loading rates were far higher than 5 g/(m².d) (Table 1 and Fig. S.1), and the average COD/ NH₄⁺-N ratio was 16.3 throughout the study. In addition, during the study, the calculated SRT of MBBR-1 was lower than 3 d, which hinders the nitrification process in MBBR-1 [40]. In the MBMBR process, NH₄⁺-N was completely oxidized to NO₃⁻-N, averaging 50±2.3 mg-N/L with no NO₂⁻-N accumulation, indicating a high nitrification performance of the MBMBR (Figs. 4a, b and d).

In period 2, HRT was decreased to 6 h, and ammonium load increased from 0.21 to 0.42 g-N/d (Table 1). With the increasing nitrogen loading rate, the complete nitrification efficiency of

1 MBMBR dropped sharply as the effluent NO_3^- -N concentration decreased from 49 mg-N/L to
2 30 mg/L, and nitrite accumulated in the permeate (Figs. 4b and d). The nitrification performance
3 of MBMBR increased within a couple of days again. While the accumulated nitrite
4 concentration decreased, the nitrate concentration rose from 30 to 44 mg-N/L. However,
5 unexpected operational problems experienced in the system starting on day 93 caused a
6 significant decrease in nitrification performance, accompanied by ammonia and nitrite
7 accumulation in the permeate (Fig. 4b). Nevertheless, nitrification performance and nitrate
8 concentration increased gradually and were almost fully restored within two weeks.

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20 In period 3 (second configuration), by keeping the total MBBRs volume the same, a second
21 MBBR (MBBR 2) was connected serially to the MBBR-1. Half of the MBBR-1's content,
22 including biocarriers, was transferred to the MBBR-2. Hence, the volume and HRT of each
23 reactor were 3.5 L and 3 h, respectively. While the surface COD loading rate was around 13.5
24 $\text{g}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d})$ in MBBR-1, it was approximately 1.0 $\text{g}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d})$ in MBBR-2 during this period (Table
25 1). The surface ammonium loading rate of MBBR-2 was 0.72 $\text{g}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d})$ (Fig. S.1). The calculated
26 total SRT of the serially connected MBBRs was 3.93 ± 0.3 days on average. To promote
27 autotrophic growth on biocarriers in MBBR-2, the sludge was recirculated at a flow rate of 2.4
28 L/h from MBR to MBBR-2 for almost two weeks. During this time, nitrification started, and
29 nitrate concentration reached 30 mg-N/L in MBBR-2. However, complete nitrification to nitrate
30 ceased, and nitrate concentration sharply decreased to zero when sludge recirculation was
31 stopped. The partial nitrification process started immediately after the recirculation pump was
32 discontinued. Nitrite started to accumulate gradually, accompanied by a decrease in ammonia
33 concentration, indicating the development of autotrophic biomass on the biocarriers in MBBR-
34 2. The nitrite concentration reached 27 mg-N/L and then oxidized to nitrate entirely within 20
35 days. Steady-state nitrate, nitrite, and ammonium concentrations during this period averaged
36 25 ± 2.6 mg-N/L, 0.42 ± 0.25 mg-N/L and 1.91 ± 0.87 mg-N/L, respectively (Figs. 4a, b and d).
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1 Results showed that complete ammonium oxidation to nitrate with a rate up to 0.67 g-N/(m².d)
2 was accomplished at very low surface COD loadings and MBBRs' SRT values higher than
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4 three days (almost 4 days).
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7 The nitrate concentration in the MBR permeate was higher than expected in this period,
8 considering the inlet nitrate and ammonia concentrations of the MBR. While the ammonium
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10 and nitrate concentrations in the outlet of MBBR-2 or inlet of the MBR were only around 2 mg-
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12 N/L and 25 mg-N/L, respectively, NO₃-N concentration was around 48 mg/L in the MBR
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14 permeate. The biomass decay rate in the MBR was calculated as 0.482 g-MLVSS/(L-MBR.d)
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16 in period 3. The increased nitrate concentration in the MBR can be attributed to the oxidation
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18 of N-containing biomass decay products. Due to biomass decay, the nitrate production rate was
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20 calculated as 0.083 g NO₃-N/(L-MBR.d), and thus, the nitrogen formation rate was calculated
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22 as 17% of the biomass decay rate, which is close to the theoretical N content of biomass, 12.4%
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24 [41]. Additionally, increased phosphate concentrations in the MBR also support this
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26 phenomenon. While the average PO₄⁻³-P concentration in MBBR-2 outlet was 1.2±0.4 mg/L, it
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28 increased to 2.5±0.5 mg/L in the MBR (Fig. 4c), resulting from biomass decay in the MBR due
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30 to high SRT and a limiting amount of substrate. Considering the nitrogen and phosphorus
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32 concentrations in the feed, the recovery efficiencies of MBMBR for nitrogen and phosphorus
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34 were as high as 45% and 78%, respectively. This result demonstrates that the MBMBR is a
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36 promising process for reusing water and recycling both nitrogen and phosphorus for irrigation
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38 purposes.
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49 Although no ammonium was detected in the permeate, the nitrate concentration in the MBR
50 slightly decreased from 50 mg-N/L to 34 mg-N/L from day 175 to day 191, when almost all
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52 ammonia was oxidized in MBBR-2. Nitrification in MBBR-2 resulted in an increase in the
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54 COD/ NH₄⁺-N ratio in the inlet of the MBR, which may promote denitrification in the MBR.
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59 Continuous aerobic operation of the MBR could gradually enrich nitrifiers and fast-growing
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1 heterotrophic bacteria, resulting in a biofilm that hinders oxygen transfer, thereby establishing
2 denitrifying conditions in the inner biofilm layer [27]. The decrease in COD (Fig. 2) and nitrate
3 concentrations (Fig. 4d) in MBR may be attributed to denitrification in the cake layer formed
4 on the membrane surface.
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10 The conventional denitrification process takes place under anoxic conditions. On the other
11 hand, aerobic denitrification is a biological process where nitrate is converted to nitrogen gas
12 using organic matter as an electron donor, occurring under aerobic conditions in a broad range
13 of dissolved oxygen concentrations performed by specific strains [42]. Moreover, it has been
14 reported that some aerobic denitrifiers, which are named denitrifying phosphate-accumulating
15 organisms (dPAO), can store polyphosphate under either aerobic or anoxic conditions by
16 deriving energy from the oxidation of external carbon sources [43]. Hence, dPAO can perform
17 simultaneous denitrification and phosphorus removal. The decrease in phosphate and nitrate
18 concentrations in the MBR (from day 175 to day 191), although less likely, might also be
19 attributed to the development of dPAOs.
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35 In period 4, the flow rate was doubled, and the HRT of the MBBRs and the MBR were halved
36 to 1.5 h and 3 h, respectively. Hence, the COD and ammonium loading rates of MBBR-2
37 increased to around 6.7 g-COD/(m².d) and 1.6 g-N/(m².d), respectively (Table 1). Besides, the
38 total calculated SRT of MBBR-1 and MBBR-2 decreased to 2.8±0.5 days. Nitrification in
39 MBBR-2 ceased sharply, and ammonia increased to 30 mg-N/L due to decreasing HRT and
40 SRT, accompanied by increasing COD loading rates higher than 5 g-COD/(m².d) (Hem et al.,
41 1994)(Hem et al., 1994)(Hem et al., 1994). Conversely, reducing the HRT from 6 h to 3 h did
42 not negatively impact the nitrification performance of the MBR. The average nitrate-nitrogen
43 concentration was 46±6 mg-N/L, with a nitrogen recovery efficiency exceeding 75%, similar
44 to that observed in period 3, likely due to biomass decay considering the total nitrogen present
45 in the feed solution.
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In the last period (period 5), the sludge recirculation from the MBR to the MBBR-2 was initiated without changing the operational conditions. The sludge recycling initiated the nitrification process again in MBBR-2, even under a short HRT. Despite a temporary decrease in nitrification efficiency in both MBBR-2 and MBR due to operational issues during this period, the nitrification performance quickly recovered once the problems were resolved. The ammonium oxidation rate in the MBBR-2 was calculated as $0.91 \text{ g- NH}_4^+\text{-N}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d})$, which was much higher than that in period-3 ($0.67 \text{ g- NH}_4^+\text{-N}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d})$), when sludge recycling was not applied. Hence, the hybrid suspended and attached growth process (IFAS) improved the nitrification rate significantly. Similarly, Trapani et al. [30] reported the nitrification rate in the IFAS process as $0.99 \text{ g- NH}_4^+\text{-N}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d})$. Average $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ concentrations of MBBR-2 and MBR, excluding the data from days where operational problems occurred, were 32 ± 4 and 48 ± 2 mg/L, respectively, with a nitrogen recovery efficiency of 78% in the MBMBR system. This result demonstrates that the MBMBR is a promising process for reusing water and recycling both nitrogen and phosphorus for irrigation purposes.

3.4. MLSS, MLVSS, and Attached Biomass Concentrations in Different MBMBR Configurations

Three different MBMBR configurations were operated under various HRTs. In the first configuration, where one MBBR was used in front of the MBR, HRTs in bioreactors were kept the same at 12 (period-1) and 6 h (period-2). The variations of MLSS and MLVSS concentrations in the bioreactors are illustrated in Figs. 5a and b.

In the MBMBR of configuration-1, MLSS and MLVSS concentrations remained relatively stable, averaging 266 ± 28 and 252 ± 33 mg/L at 12 h HRT and 259 ± 115 and 256 ± 102 mg/L at 6

1 h HRT, respectively. In configuration-2, two serially connected MBBRs were operated at the
2 same HRTs of 3 h (period-3) and 1.5 h (period-4). However, MLSS and MLVSS concentrations
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4 in the MBBRs did not change appreciably. MLSS concentrations at HRTs of 3 and 1.5 h
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6 averaged 258 ± 47 and 235 ± 19 in MBBR-1 and 208 ± 40 and 205 ± 13 mg/L in MBBR-2,
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8 respectively. Similarly, MLVSS concentrations averaged 227 ± 46 and 215 ± 17 in MBBR-1 and
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10 170 ± 44 and 177 ± 6 mg/L in MBBR-2, respectively. Hence, slight decreases in both MLSS and
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12 MLVSS concentrations were observed in the MBBR-2 compared to the MBBR-1, which may
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14 be due to the attachment of biomass sloughed off from the MBBR-1 to the biocarriers in the
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16 MBBR-2. Similar results were reported in the literature about the low biomass concentration in
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18 the effluent of conventional MBBRs. In the study of [44], MLSS and MLVSS concentrations
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20 in the MBBRs were reported in the range of 250-260 mg/L and 240-250 mg/L, respectively.
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22 Similarly, [23] reported that the average suspended solid concentrations in the outlet of MBBR
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24 were 88 and 126 mg/L at low and high rates, respectively.
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31 In the last configuration, where sludge was recycled from MBR to the MBBR-2, HRT in the
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33 MBBRs was kept the same at 1.5 h and it was 3 h in the MBR. MLSS and MLVSS
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35 concentrations in the MBBR-1 were quite similar, averaging 208 ± 35 and 180 ± 36 mg/L,
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37 respectively (Fig. 5a). Sludge recirculation from the MBR increased the MLSS and MLVSS
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39 concentrations in the MBBR-2 to 6369 ± 530 and 5357 ± 524 mg/L, respectively (Fig. 5a). Hence,
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41 hybridization with sludge recycling allowed the use of both suspended and attached growth
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43 biomass within the MBBR-2.
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49 In the outlet of MBBR-1, the MLVSS concentration averaged 236 ± 66 mg/L throughout the
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51 operation and did not vary significantly with HRT, as discussed above in detail. Assuming
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53 steady-state conditions in the attached phase, the SRT was calculated as around 3 d in period-
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55 1, which decreased to 2.3 ± 0.5 and 2.4 ± 0.2 in periods-2 and -3, respectively. It is interesting to
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57 observe similar SRT in periods-2 and -3 although HRT decreased from 6 to 3 h, respectively.
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In periods-4 and -5, HRT in the MBBR-1 was kept the same at 1.5 h, and a noteworthy decrease in SRT to 1.4 ± 0.5 d was observed. In the MBBR-1, the observed yield coefficient (Y_{obs}) was quite high, averaging 0.52 ± 0.16 g-MLVSS/g-COD throughout the operation due to the low SRTs (1.5-3 d). High Y_{obs} values at short SRTs were reported in previous studies [32,45]. Most of the COD was depleted in the MBBR-1, as discussed before, which led to a limiting amount of substrate in the following units. The long SRTs and limiting amount of substrate in the MBR resulted in biomass decay, which led to a significant decrease in the overall Y_{obs} value, which was discussed below.

Attached biomass concentrations as g-SS/m² were illustrated in Fig. 5c. At the end of the first phase, where HRT was 12 h, the attached biomass concentration was 4.1 g-SS/m², corresponding to around 1.2 g-SS/L within the MBBR-1. As discussed previously, the suspended biomass concentration was around 0.25 g/L, which means attached biomass in the MBBR was primarily responsible for the treatment. When HRT decreased to 6 h, biomass concentration on the carrier increased substantially, which was due to increased organic loading, to around 11 ± 3 g-SS/m². Hence, the attached biomass concentration in terms of bioreactor volume increased from 1.2 to around 3.2 g/L with decreasing HRT (Fig. 5c). Although attached biomass concentration increased three times with decreasing HRT, suspended biomass concentration at the outlet of the MBBR in periods-1 and -2 was almost similar, averaging 266 and 259 mg/L, respectively. Hence, even though the organic loading rate and total biomass concentration increased, the suspended solid concentration in the liquid phase flowing to subsequent units (settling tank or membrane) remained unchanged. This is one of the advantages of the MBBR process over conventional suspended growth processes, as it allows the upgrading of existing conventional processes safely and easily. With decreasing the HRT in the MBBR-1 (configuration-2) to 3 h, the attached biomass concentration increased to 15 ± 2.1 g-SS/m², corresponding to 4.50 ± 0.6 g/L. Hence, decreasing HRT led to a significant

1 increase in attached biomass concentrations, while suspended biomass concentrations remained
2 unaffected. Later, decreasing HRT in the MBBR-1 further to 1.5 h in period-4 (configuration-
3 2) and period-5 (configuration-3) caused the attached biomass concentration to increase to 18 ± 4
4 g/m^2 , corresponding to 5.3 ± 1 g/L total biomass. Although decreasing HRT from 3 h (period-3)
5 to 1.5 h (periods-4 and -5) doubled the loading rate, the attached biomass concentration on the
6 carrier increased by around 15%, which may be due to reaching the maximum biomass carrying
7 capacity of the plastic material ($\sim 20\text{-}25$ g-SS/m²). Hence, using more than one MBBR in series
8 with high loading results in the use of biocarriers at maximum capacity, which allows for more
9 economical process design.
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22 A second MBBR was put into operation after period-3 (configuration-2). MBBR-2 was mainly
23 used for the nitrification process in period-3, as the COD concentration in the outlet of MBBR-
24 1 (averaged around 40 mg/L) was very low for heterotrophic biomass growth on the biocarriers
25 in MBBR-2 (Fig. 2). Whereas the ammonium concentration was 27 mg/L in the outlet of the
26 MBBR-1 and decreased to around 2 mg/L in the outlet of the MBBR-2 (Fig. 4a). Hence, the
27 biofilm developed on the biocarriers in MBBR-2 was mainly autotrophic organisms. One of the
28 main advantages of the staged MBBR process is the development of specific biomass in
29 separate bioreactors, as also noted previously by others [12,46]. The biofilm amount on the
30 carriers in MBBR-2 was 7.6 ± 2.4 g/m² in period-3 (Fig. 5c). Hence, the autotrophic biomass
31 was maintained in the MBBR-2 safely when the organic matter was previously removed in the
32 MBBR-1. In the next period (period-4), HRT in each MBBR was decreased to 1.5 h, which led
33 to COD in the outlet of MBBR-1 increasing from around 40 to 125 mg/L. Hence, higher organic
34 matter was fed to the MBBR-2 in period-4. This resulted in decreased nitrification performance
35 significantly, as ammonium in the MBBR-2 increased from around 2 to 30 mg/L, and hence
36 nitrate in the outlet of MBBR-2 decreased from 25 to 1.2 mg/L. Therefore, biomass in period-
37 4 may have shifted from autotrophic to heterotrophic biomass. Increasing organic matter
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1 loading in period-4 resulted in the biomass amount on biocarriers increasing to 10.6 ± 2.9 g/m²,
2 corresponding to 3.2 ± 0.9 g/L (Fig. 5c). As discussed before, the suspended biomass
3 concentrations in the effluent of MBBR-2 were close to 0.2 g/L; hence, attached biomass was
4 mainly responsible for the biodegradation. In period-5, where configuration-3 was put into
5 operation under similar conditions except for sludge recycling, biomass concentration on the
6 biocarriers decreased to around 5 ± 1.3 g/m², which was due to the increased competition
7 between suspended and attached growth biomass for the same substrate. Starting sludge
8 recirculation increased the suspended biomass concentration in the MBBR-2 to around 6400
9 mg/L (Fig. 5a), which increased the competition between the suspended and attached biomass
10 for COD and ammonium. Hence, the attached biomass concentration on the biocarriers
11 decreased appreciably in period-5. Hybridization with sludge recycling to MBBR-2 led to the
12 resumption of the nitrification process, even at a short HRT.

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30 In the MBR process, SRT was kept constant at 20 d throughout the operation. In the first period,
31 where HRT in the MBR was 12 h, MLSS and MLVSS averaged 3093 ± 139 and 2485 ± 181 mg/L,
32 respectively. According to mass balance, MLVSS concentration in the MBR should be around
33 10 g/L, whereas it was measured as around 2.5 g/L. Hence, it seems that biomass decayed in
34 the MBR due to a limiting amount of substrate. The biomass decay rate in the MBR was
35 calculated as around 0.38 g-MLVSS/(L-MBR.d). In period-2, HRT in the MBR decreased to 6
36 h, which led to MLSS and MLVSS concentrations increasing to 5285 ± 631 and 4534 ± 555 mg/L,
37 respectively (Fig. 5b). In period-3, HRT in the MBR was kept constant at 6 h, and both MLSS
38 and MLVSS concentrations stayed similar at 4813 ± 342 and 3990 ± 248 mg/L, respectively. The
39 biomass decay rate in the MBR was calculated as 0.482 g-MLVSS/(L-MBR.d). In period-4,
40 decreasing HRT to 3 h resulted in increasing MLSS and MLVSS concentrations to 10120 ± 321
41 and 8660 ± 53 mg/L, respectively (Fig. 5). Recycling sludge from MBR to MBBR-2 in period-
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5, did not change the biomass concentration significantly, as MLSS and MLVSS concentrations averaged 11273 ± 1208 and 9522 ± 1097 mg/L, respectively.

The Y_{obs} of the whole process throughout the operation did not vary significantly and averaged 0.11 ± 0.01 g-VSS/g-COD. In the study of [47], Y_{obs} at SRTs 20 and 30 d were reported as 0.148 and 0.102 g-VSS/g-COD, respectively. In the present study, Y_{obs} value was very similar to that observed by [47] at an SRT of 30 d. This may result from the increased total SRT in the whole system due to the attached growth in the MBBRs. Total system SRT varied between 28 and 35 d and averaged 32 ± 3 d. Hence, the increase in total SRT due to attached biomass growth led to a decrease in sludge generation, an increase in biomass decay, and elevated nitrate production, which were also discussed in 3.3. Hence, the average Y_{obs} (0.11 g-VSS/g-COD) of the MBMBR is very close to that observed by [47] at an SRT of 30 d (0.102 g-VSS/g-COD).

3.5.EPS, SMP, CST, and viscosity variations in the membrane tank of the MBMBR process

SMP and EPS variations in each reactor and period were illustrated in Fig. S.2. SMP concentrations in the MBBR-1 did not change significantly and averaged 8.4 ± 2.9 mg-COD/L. In the MBBR-2, SMP concentration was around 12 mg-COD/L in period 4 and increased to around 40 mg-COD/L with the MBR recycle, which means some SMP may also be transported with the recycle to the MBBR-2. SMP concentration in the membrane unit is of great importance in terms of membrane filtration performance. SMP concentrations in periods-1 and 2 were 12 and 47 mg-COD/L, respectively. Hence, decreasing HRT from 12 to 6 h resulted in increasing SMP almost four times (Fig. S.2). Hence, although treatment performance did not vary significantly, SMP concentration, which may have an impact on membrane fouling, significantly increased. In the membrane tank, SMP in both periods was significantly rejected, as their concentrations were around 4 and 9 mg/L COD in the permeate. Hence, most of the SMP was biologically degraded or physically retained in the membrane tank. In the third period,

1 a second MBBR was added to the process, and HRT in the MBR was kept constant at 6 h. This
2 decreased the SMP in the membrane tank to around 27 mg-COD/L, which illustrated that
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4 connecting the MBBRs in series also decreased the SMP concentration in the supernatant. In
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6 period 4, halving the HRT in the process significantly increased the SMP concentration to 94
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8 mg/L, which means the fouling tendency of the supernatant increased. In the last period, sludge
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10 was recycled from MBR to MBBR-2 to hybridize the process, in which both suspended and
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12 attached growth biomass were utilized in the process. This configuration decreased SMP to
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14 around 57 mg/L, which means that the IFAS-MBR process (process with recycle) may perform
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16 better than the MBMBR process in terms of membrane filtration performance.
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22 In MBBR-1, total EPS concentrations varied between 72 and 196 mg-COD/(g-MLVSS)
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24 depending on the operational conditions. It was around 196 mg-COD/(g-MLVSS) and
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26 decreased to around 86 mg-COD/(g-MLVSS) in periods-1 and -2, respectively. In periods-4
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28 and period-5, MBBR-1 was operated under the same conditions at an HRT of 1.5 h. The average
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30 EPS concentration during periods 4 and 5 was around 110 mg-COD/(g-MLVSS). Throughout
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32 the reactor operation, the total EPS concentration averaged 121 ± 44 mg-COD/(g-MLVSS). The
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34 EPS concentrations in the second bioreactor were much lower compared to those in MBBR-1,
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36 which should be due to the use of EPS in MBBR-2 as a carbon source under famine conditions.
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38 The use of EPS in the MBBR-2 may have caused an increase in the SMP concentration, as it
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40 averaged around 7.5 mg/L in MBBR-1 and 29 mg-COD/L in MBBR-2 during period-3. In the
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42 MBR supernatant, EPS concentrations did not show a significant change throughout the
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44 operation and averaged 49 ± 13 mg-COD/(g-MLVSS). The SRT in the MBR was kept at 20 d,
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46 which led to the decay of biomass. Long SRT in the MBR caused increased EPS concentration
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48 in the MBR process.
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57 Variations on SMP and EPS concentrations in each unit of MBMBR are illustrated in Table 2.

58 The carbohydrate fraction of SMP in MBBR-1 was around 60%, whereas a noteworthy increase
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1 in the carbohydrate fraction in MBBR-2 and MBR were observed. Considering 90% of SMP
2 rejection by the membrane, it may be expected that the cake layer should have been mainly
3 composed of carbohydrates. A higher carbohydrate fraction of SMP in the supernatant of the
4 MBR was also observed previously in the study of [32].
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10 The fraction of loosely bound EPS in the MBBR-1 was around 33%; however, it significantly
11 decreased in the MBBR-1 and MBR to around 14–15%. On the contrary, the carbohydrate
12 fraction of loosely bound EPS increased from around 34% in the MBBR-1 to 48–49% in the
13 MBBR-2 and MBR. Similarly, the carbohydrate fraction of tightly bound EPS was around 43%,
14 which increased to 66–69% in the MBBR-2 and MBR. Hence, in the MBBR-2 and MBR, both
15 EPS and SMP are mainly composed of carbohydrates.
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25 Viscosities in periods 2-4 did not show any noteworthy change and averaged 4.1 ± 0.7 cP.
26 Whereas it significantly increased to 14 ± 4.8 cP in period-5 (Fig. 6c), which should be due to
27 both increased biomass concentration and changing supernatant characteristics.
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33 **3.6. Membrane Filtration Performance**

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36 The SRF value was lowest in the first period (Fig. 6b), which supports having the lowest SMP
37 in the supernatant and the highest SF in period-1. Decreasing HRT in the following periods
38 resulted in increases in the SRF values. Adding sludge recycling in period-5, decreased SRF
39 significantly (Fig. 6b), similar to the decrease in SMP concentration (Fig. S.2). Hence, the
40 filtration tests (SRF and SF) and SMP concentrations were highly correlated. It seems that
41 bioreactor operating conditions impact both supernatant and sludge characteristics, which
42 subsequently affect the filtration performance.
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53 Similar to the results of SMP, SF, and SRF, the lowest value of CST was observed in period-1
54 as 16 ± 3 s (Fig. 6c). In the following periods, it increased and averaged 43 ± 15 s in periods-2, 3
55 and 4. However, in the last period, it increased appreciably to its maximum of 140 ± 31 s in
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period-5. These results were consistent with those of viscosity, as it was similar in periods 2-4 and increased appreciably in the last period (Fig. 6c). Hence, an increase in viscosity led to a decrease in the dewaterability of sludge, which means increasing the CST.

In addition to the characteristics of the sludge and supernatant, biomass concentration has an impact on filtration performance, as higher biomass concentrations cause thicker cake formation. The filtration results at 0.5 bar for each period are illustrated in Fig. 6a. Similar to SRF and SF, the highest filtration performance was observed in period-1. During the filtration tests, MLSS concentration was much lower in period 1 (~3 g/L). In periods-2 and -3, MLSS concentrations (5.7 and 5 g/L, respectively) and the filtration results are similar. In agreement with this finding, the lowest and similar filtration performances were observed in periods-4 and -5, where MLSS concentrations were around 10 and 12 g/L, respectively, during the filtration tests. Therefore, both characteristics and concentration of biomass are important in filtration performance. As illustrated in Fig. S.2, SMP in the MBR unit was at its lowest concentration in period-1 and increased in the following periods, reaching its maximum in period-4. Similar to these findings, supernatant filterability was at its maximum in period-1 (2.1 mL/min) and in the following periods, it averaged 0.78 ± 0.07 mL/min (Fig. 6a). Hence, as the SMP in the supernatant increased, its filterability decreased.

The TMP variation of the membrane unit in the MBMBR process is illustrated in Fig. S.3. Depending on the HRT in the MBR, flux varied between 2.5 (HRT = 12 h) and 10 LMH (HRT = 3 h). On day 102, critical flux was determined to be between 30 and 35 LMH, as no obvious increase in TMP was observed at 30 LMH and it increased sharply at 35 LMH (data not shown). The relatively high critical flux in the process was partially due to the high aeration rate in the MBR, which was around $2.5 \text{ m}^3\text{-air}/(\text{m}^2\text{-membrane.h})$. In a recent study with the same membrane, [47] reported the critical flux as 20-30 LMH at an aeration rate of $0.78 \text{ m}^3\text{-air}/(\text{m}^2\text{-membrane.h})$ in an MBR treating textile wastewater at various SRTs. In the study, TMP

1 increased up to 110 mbar on day 78, and after physical cleaning, it decreased back to 10 mbar.
2 On day 130, TMP sharply increased up to 400 mbar; after physical cleaning, it decreased back
3 to around 10 mbar and remained almost unchanged up to day 242, when it sharply increased up
4 to 700 mbar. A chemical cleaning was then applied to remove irreversible fouling on the
5 membrane, which may have developed due to long-term operation. After chemical cleaning,
6 TMP stayed stable at 10 mbar until the end of the operation. Relatively low fouling in the
7 membrane can be attributed to operating the MBR at fluxes well below the critical flux,
8 applying a high aeration/scouring rate in the membrane tank, and oxidizing a significant portion
9 of organic matter in previous biofilm processes.
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22 **4. Conclusion**

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25 This study focuses on comparing different MBMBR process configurations in terms of process
26 performance and the potential of nutrient recycling from wastewater for agricultural irrigation
27 purposes. The results may serve as a guide for optimizing the operation of the MBMBR process.
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30 Conclusions are summarized as follows:
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35 **1.** Serially connected MBBRs at high loadings increase the capacity of biocarriers (up to
36 20-25 g-SS/m²), enabling a more economical process design.
37
- 38 **2.** The MBMBR, with or without sludge recirculation, achieves complete nitrification with
39 a rate of 0.91 and 0.67 g- NH₄⁺-N/m², respectively, and maximizes nutrient recycling
40 and water reuse potentials for irrigation.
41
- 42 **3.** The MBMBR process performs better than traditional MBBR and MBR processes,
43 providing higher treatment capacity up to 98% COD removal, complete nitrification,
44 and reduced membrane fouling.
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- 46 **4.** The IFAS-MBR (configuration-3) process gives better performance than the MBMBR
47 process in terms of nitrification capacity and membrane filtration performance.
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Declaration of AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used the QuillBot tool to partially improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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List of Tables

Table 1. Operational conditions of the MBMBR

	Periods	Configuration-1		Configuration-2		Configuration-3*
		1	2	3	4	5
	Days	11-64	65-128	129-186	187-121	222-270
	Flux (LMH)	2.5	5.0	5.0	10.0	10.0
HRT (h)	MBBR-1	12	6	3	1.5	1.5
	MBBR-2	-	-	3	1.5	1.5
	MBR	12	6	6	3	3
COD loadings (g/m ² .d)	MBBR-1	3.5±0.2	7.2±0.5	13.5±0.1	27±0.3	28±1.2
	MBBR-2	-	-	1.0±0.2	6.7±0.8	7.3±2.1
NH ₄ ⁺ -N loadings (g-N/m ² .d)	MBBR-1**	0.21±0.02	0.42±0.05	0.84±0.05	1.78±0.04	1.72±0.03
	MBBR-2	-	-	0.72±0.03	1.59±0.11	1.64±0.08

*Sludge was recycled at a flow rate of 2.4 L/h

**Total nitrogen loads are approximately two times high.

Table 2. SMP and EPS concentrations in each unit of MBMBR

Parameter	MBBR-1	MBBR-2	MBR-supernatant	MBR-permeate
SMP				
Total SMP	8.4±2.9	26.4±14.9	45.8±25.4	4.8±6.2
SMP-P	3.3±1.3	1.1±1.7	1.6±2.7	0.4±0.4
SMP-C	5.2±1.9	25.3±16.4	44.3±23.4	4.5±6.4
EPS				
LB-EPS	37.4±18.8	2.1±0.5	6.8±3.3	
EPS-P	24.7±13.6	1.1±0.4	3.5±2.7	
EPS-C	12.7±6.5	1.0±0.8	3.3±0.8	
TB-EPS	77.2±32.6	12.1±11.7	41.8±13.1	
EPS-P	43.9±22.4	4.2±1.9	13.1±3.6	
EPS-C	33.3±14.4	8.0±10.0	28.7±12.1	

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Figure 1. Schematic of the MBMBR process configurations

Figure 2. COD variations in different units of the MBMBR throughout the operation

Figure 3. Alkalinity variations in different units of the MBMBR throughout the operation

Figure 4. a) $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$, b) $\text{NO}_2^-\text{-N}$, c) $\text{PO}_4^{3-}\text{-P}$ and d) $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ variations in different units of the MBMBR process

Figure 5. MLSS, MLVSS of a) MBBRs, and b) MBR and c) attached biomass variations in MBBRs

Figure 6. Variations of a) filtration performances b) SF, SRF, c) CST and viscosity values of MBR for each period

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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